

MAKING HIV PREVENTION WORK:

How Can Programmes be Improved to Support Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP) Use & Adherence in sub-Saharan Africa.

Implementer Brief

Introduction

PrEP is a highly effective HIV prevention method, reducing the risk of HIV acquisition by over 90% when taken consistently, but its efficacy is contingent on consistent adherence. While awareness campaigns and policy efforts have successfully increased PrEP uptake, high rates of discontinuation continue to undermine its public health impact. This highlights why adherence, not just uptake, is critical for PrEP effectiveness.

Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) faces unique challenges, including structural inequality, healthcare resource limitations, and sociocultural dynamics that require tailored approaches beyond clinical trial settings. Effective use and adherence remain a challenge. PrEP's potential is undermined when individuals disengage or do not use it during periods of increased risk. Questions emerge about what strategies have been effective in supporting effective use of PrEP, and what the lessons are for programme implementers.

We conducted a [review](#) aimed at identifying effective interventions and implementation strategies that support effective use of PrEP in SSA.

Key Takeaways

- **Prioritise user choice and agency** - Implement comprehensive choice-based counselling and ensure multi-modality availability (oral, ring, injectable) so users can select options that best align with their individual context and risk periods.
- **Offer differentiated and repeated support services** - Train providers for brief, repeated, and tailored adherence counselling sessions to address evolving personal, social, and product-specific challenges over time.
- **Minimise logistical barriers** - Introduce flexible delivery models, including multi-month dispensing (MMD), mobile delivery, and community-based dispensing, to simplify the PrEP journey and reduce PrEP drop-outs.
- **Integrate and normalise services** - Embed PrEP discussions and services into routine, non-HIV care settings (e.g., family planning, maternal and child health, gender-based violence, STI clinics) to reduce stigma and improve service acceptability.
- **Leverage accessible technology** - Utilise simple, practical, and locally appropriate technology, such as tailored SMS reminders and phone calls, to provide timely prompts and support that address adherence fatigue.

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Scope of the review

A variety of intervention packages have been implemented to support PrEP adherence and effective use. We looked at how the interventions address adherence barriers at an individual level, healthcare provider and system level, as well as at a community level.

Figure 1: Number of studies included in the review by country

- **Forty (40) peer-reviewed articles from PubMed (2019-2025) focusing on PrEP adherence and support in 9 South-to-South Learning Network (SSLN) countries** were included in the review, see figure 1 above for distribution.
- Most evidence comes from **Kenya** (16 studies), **Uganda** (15 studies), and **South Africa** (11 studies), with fewer from **Eswatini** (1), **Malawi** (2), **Nigeria** (1), **Tanzania** (1), **Zambia** (2), and **Zimbabwe** (2).

Access more information on the methodology by clicking [here](#).

The results are underpinned by a [framework](#) that highlights context-specific approaches that address both user needs and health system approaches.

Findings

Overall, more than half of the studies (22 out of 40) reported an improvement in PrEP adherence. Of these, 10 used objective measures such as drug-level testing. Of the studies reviewed, interventions that focused on individual PrEP users were the most tested (14); followed by multi-level interventions (11) and interventions that combined individual level with health care interventions (8), with a smaller number testing other models. **Using the more objective measures, the combination of individual-level and healthcare interventions seems to yield the best PrEP adherence outcomes.**

Figure 2 presents the tested adherence intervention types and the number of studies that showed improvements in PrEP adherence outcome by type of measure.

Figure 2: Interventions implemented that successfully increased adherence

Intervention approaches that have worked:

Individual Level Interventions

Successful individual interventions address education on effective use of the PrEP method, personalised counselling, risk assessment, and personal readiness.

Figure 3 below details successful individual interventions that were most commonly implemented and effective at improving PrEP adherence.

- Individual adherence counseling was most commonly used and was most successful in supporting effective PrEP use when it included motivational interviewing, personal agency and trusted relationships with healthcare providers.
- PrEP education and awareness was used to address personal concerns & support users to make informed, proactive decisions about their own health.
- Reminder systems such as phone calls or text messages, provided timely prompts for users to take their medication and return for refills. However, users faced structural barriers, such as network challenges, access to electricity, access to (smart)phones and SMS fatigue.
- Peer or mentor support such as "adherence supporters" were used to address myths and misconceptions about PrEP, reduce stigma and build collective understanding.

Intervention approaches that worked:

Healthcare provider-level Interventions:

- Increased provider knowledge of PrEP options to meet PrEP preferences of the target population.
- Training on PrEP eligibility and clinical management.
- Stigma reduction activities with healthcare providers to provide non-judgmental care.
- Enabling health providers to adapt service delivery in flexible ways (e.g. later clinic hours, community-based outreach, different cadre of providers who are able to counsel on and provide PrEP).

Community Interventions:

Successful community-level interventions address **PrEP-related stigma, negative social norms around sexual practices**, and **foster supportive environments** for PrEP use through community leader engagement and mobilisation, peer-led outreach and support, including stigma reduction campaigns.

However, community-level efforts alone were not sufficient. Studies with improved adherence consistently combined community interventions with individual-level support.

DREAMS programming in Kenya used community mobilisation and male partner engagement to enhance PrEP persistence amongst adolescents and young women (AGYW). They planned meetings at communal centres with local chiefs and parents to build PrEP support, popularised "buddy days" to engage couples in safe spaces and offered routine health services to reduce stigma.

Figure 3: Successful individual interventions for PrEP adherence and support

Socio-cultural context considerations

A "one-size-fits-all" approach to PrEP adherence is insufficient; interventions must be tailored to the unique needs, behaviours, and social realities of specific populations.

AGYW

- Dynamic HIV risk perception.
- High mobility & unpredictable schedules.
- Anticipated PrEP-related stigma.
- Anticipated social stigma re: sexual activity.

Counselling that addresses fluctuating risk perceptions, guide AGYW on 'rational PrEP use' and PrEP choice to fit lifestyle, and supplement with community-level support for PrEP use.

ABM

- Low perceived HIV risk.
- Transient lifestyle.
- Concerns about PrEP side effects & impact on daily life.
- Negative perceptions about PrEP.

Tailored multi-level support addressing mobility, substance use, multiple prevention needs. Tech tools for awareness & adherence. Sensitisation of healthcare providers.

MSM & LGBTQI+

- Persistent societal stigma.
- Judgemental and non-discreet health services.
- Adherence challenges & preference for non-daily PrEP formulations.

Choice-based delivery models incorporating long-acting forms of PrEP, alternative delivery methods, and discreet, affirming care supported by peer-led models to enhance access.

PWIDs

[Very limited evidence & insights]

- Multiple health & support needs.
- Restrictive access to health facilities and services.
- Social stigma.
- Legal barriers.

Discreet and confidential care in community-based settings.

FSWs

- Multiple prevention needs (contraception, STIs, HIV).
- Substance abuse.
- Low community awareness on PrEP.
- Restrictive health facility policies.
- Judgemental health services & inconvenient hours.

Targeted PrEP education, mobile (non-facility based) delivery, long-acting PrEP options, and partner support for improved uptake & adherence.

Recommendations for programme implementers

To enhance the effectiveness, accessibility, and acceptability of PrEP, the following user-centred strategies are recommended, each designed to empower personal choice, support sustained adherence, and integrate PrEP seamlessly into everyday health systems and routines. Programme implementers may consider the following:

1 Empower choice.

Offer choice-based counselling that supports personal agency and addresses product-specific concerns and fears. Allow users to choose what fits their context and preferences.

2 Offer tailored adherence support.

Train providers for brief, repeat counselling sessions to address evolving adherence challenges and PrEP needs.

3 Reduce logistical burdens.

Use mobile delivery, multi-month dispensing, and community dispensing to make it easier for users to stay engaged with PrEP.

4 Normalise PrEP.

Embed in routine (non-HIV) care interactions to improve user experience and reduce stigma.

5 Use simple technology.

Leverage SMS reminders or phone calls, or other tech that is accessible and practical and tailored to local infrastructure.

Additional Resources

Suggested Citation

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To access more information on the review, see below:

- [Overview Brief](#)
- [Methodology Brief](#)
- [Learning brief for Programme Implementers](#)
- [Learning Brief for Ministry of Health and National AIDS Commission Officials](#)

The full rapid review slide deck can be accessed [here](#).